

Insight into the Mechanism of Calcium-Induced Blockage of Gramicidin A Ion Channels

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ABSTRACT

The interaction of calcium ions with gramicidin A (gA) ion channels represents a fundamental process with significant implications for understanding ion channel regulation in biological membranes. This study employs electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (SEIRAS), and Langmuir trough experiments to unravel the multifaceted mechanism of calcium-induced blockage of gA channels in a DOPC lipid bilayer. The findings reveal that calcium ions interact with the polar headgroups of DOPC lipids, inducing dehydration and increased packing density, which reduce the mobility of gramicidin monomers. Structural analysis highlights significant elongation of the gA helices, weakening of hydrogen bonds, and a shift in the conformational equilibrium towards inactive monomeric forms. These observations challenge the conventional view of calcium ion blockage being solely due to steric hindrance, proposing instead a broader mechanism involving alterations in both the membrane environment and peptide structure. This novel perspective on calcium-ion-induced ion channel modulation provides valuable insights for designing biomimetic systems and developing therapeutic strategies targeting ion channel dysfunction.

1. Introduction

Gramicidin A (gA) is a linear pentadecapeptide with the following sequence of amino acids: formyl-L-Val-Gly-L-Ala-D-Leu-L-Ala-D-Val-L-Val-D-Val-L-Trp-D-Leu-L-Trp-D-Leu-L-Trp-D-Leu-L-Trp-ethanolamine.[1] This peptide is extensively utilized as a model system for investigating ion channel dynamics and functionality due to its structural simplicity

and robust ion-conducting properties.[2–6] Its unique sequence of alternating L- and D-amino acids enables gA to fold into a right-handed β -helix stabilized by a β -sheet hydrogen bonding network. This structural organization underlies gA functional polymorphism, which allows it to adopt various secondary structures in lipid bilayers. In its most prominent $\beta^{6.3}$ conformation, gramicidin peptides dimerize within the lipid bilayer, spanning the membrane and forming ion-conductive channels. The polar peptide groups line the interior of the helix, creating a hydrophilic water-filled lumen for ion translocation, while the hydrophobic side chains project outward into the lipid matrix. Hydrogen bonds formed between the indole rings of tryptophan residues and the polar headgroups of phospholipids stabilize the orientation of gA within the bilayer, with the C-terminus facing the membrane surface and the N-terminus aligned with the hydrophobic bilayer interior. The $\beta^{6.3}$ dimer configuration is further stabilized by six intramolecular hydrogen bonds between the N-termini of two helices located in opposing bilayer leaflets. This well-defined conformation is now widely accepted as the active form responsible for ion channel function, facilitating the selective transport of monovalent cations such as Na^+ and K^+ across the membrane. In contrast, gA can also adopt the $\beta^{5.6}$ conformation, a double-stranded helix characterized by tightly intertwined peptides. This conformation lacks the water-filled lumen required for ion conduction, rendering it non-conductive. The dynamic equilibrium between these conformations is highly sensitive to the surrounding lipid bilayer properties, such as hydration, thickness, and composition.[7–9] This makes gA an exceptional model system for exploring the intricate interplay between peptide conformation, membrane properties, and the mechanisms underlying ion channel activity modulation. In this study, we specifically demonstrate how calcium ions can effectively modulate and block the activity of gramicidin A channels, shedding light on the molecular mechanisms driving this interaction.

Calcium ions (Ca^{2+}), in particular, play a critical role in modulating both membrane properties and ion channel behavior. These divalent cations interact with lipid bilayers by binding to phosphate and carbonyl groups in lipid headgroups, leading to bilayer condensation, increased acyl chain ordering, and reduced hydration.[10–12] Despite extensive studies on calcium's impact on membrane properties, its precise effects on the conformation and functionality of gA channels remain incompletely understood. The widely accepted model of calcium-induced blockage postulates that Ca^{2+} ions interact directly with the entrance of the gA channel, physically obstructing the lumen and preventing the passage of monovalent cations such as Na^+ or K^+ . [13,14] This model suggests that the calcium ion's charge and size play critical roles in impeding ion flux through the channel. While this direct interaction is considered the

primary mechanism of blockage, it is increasingly recognized that calcium ions may also exert more complex effects on the surrounding lipid bilayer, indirectly altering gA's structural dynamics and functional equilibrium. This gap in knowledge underscores the need for a detailed investigation of how calcium-mediated modulation of lipid bilayers translates into changes in gA ion channel behavior. This study seeks to elucidate the molecular mechanisms underlying calcium-induced modulation of gramicidin A ion channel activity in model lipid bilayers. By combining advanced spectroscopic and electrochemical techniques, such as electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (SEIRAS), with complementary lipid monolayer studies, we aim to provide new insights into how calcium ions influence the lipid environment and the structural equilibrium of gramicidin A. These findings contribute to a broader understanding of ion channel regulation by divalent cations and have potential implications for designing biomimetic systems and therapeutic interventions targeting ion channel dysfunction.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Reagents

Hydrofluoric acid, sodium tetrachloroaurate, sodium thiosulfate, deuterium oxide, and Gramicidin A (gA) were purchased from Merck Life Science Sp. z o.o., Poznan, Poland. 1,2-dioleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DOPC), chitosan oligosaccharide lactate (low molecular weight $M_n \sim 5000$), lipoic acid, N-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS), deuterium oxide 99.5% (D_2O) was purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids Inc., Alabaster, AL, USA. All other reagents and solvents were obtained from Avantor Performance Materials Poland S.A., Gliwice, Poland (chloroform, sodium sulfite, magnesium and calcium chloride). The water was purified through the Milli-Q system (resistivity $18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \times \text{cm}$). In all experiments, we used an aqueous solution of 0.01 M PBS made in D_2O or H_2O .

2.2. Preparation of samples

The supported lipid membranes were formed by spreading the DOPC liposomes or DOPC-gA proteoliposomes on the gold surface pre-modified by chitosan-lipoic acid conjugate. Proteoliposomes were prepared according to the protocol described by Zhen Li et al [15]. 10 mg ml^{-1} of DOPC lipid with 10 % Gramicidin A was transferred to the vial and mixed with 200 microliter of chloroform. Then lipid-protein mixture was dried under a stream of argon gas to form a thin lipid film on the walls of vials. Subsequently lipid film was hydrated in a 1 ml buffer

solution (0.01 M PBS) to create unilamellar vesicles. The hydrating step took place in the sonicator at 37°C for 60 minutes. For the preparation of membranes without gramicidin (liposomes), the procedure followed was analogous to the above-mentioned method, with the exception that gA was omitted from the DOPC solution. The synthesis of chitosan-lipoic acid (ChLL) was already described by Pawłowski et al [16]. Briefly, in the initial stage of synthesis, a saturated solution of lipoic acid was prepared and activated with EDC and NHS. Subsequently, a solution of chitosan oligosaccharide lactate was adjusted to pH 5.5 and combined with the activated lipoic acid solution. The resulting mixture underwent coupling under ambient conditions for 24 hours. The resulting product, abbreviated as ChLL, was precipitated, separated, and verified by FTIR analysis, which revealed the presence of the amide I band at 1655cm^{-1} . During the reaction, the degree of *N*-acetylation increases typically from 10% in the starting compound to approximately 60% in ChLL. The yield of the coupling reaction was determined to be around 50%, indicating that half of the amine groups were bonded to lipoic acid, while about 40% remained free.

2.3. Electrochemical experiments

First, the gold electrodes were cleaned in piranha solution ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4:\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$ 3:1 v/v) for at least 12h. Then they were thoroughly rinsed with ultrapure water and flame annealed. To create a polymer cushion layer, cleaned gold electrodes were immersed in modified chitosan (ChLL) solution (dissolved in 8% acetic acid) for at least 2 hours. For further use, the electrodes were incubated in proteoliposome (or liposome) suspension overnight (~16h), and before the experiments, electrodes were gently immersed in Mili-Q water. CHI 750B potentiostat (CH Instruments, Inc., Austin, TX) was used to control applied potential. All experiments were conducted in a standard three-electrode cell configuration. The platinum foil was used as the counter electrode and $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}|1.0\text{ M KCl aq.}$ was used as a reference electrode. To remove the dissolved oxygen from the electrolyte, the solution was purged by argon. Single crystal Au (111) electrodes were used as working electrodes (MaTeck, Jülich, Germany) in a hanging meniscus configuration. The EIS measurements were performed within the frequency range of $10^{-1} - 10^4$ Hz at the potentials between 0.2 and -0.4 V with the step of -0.1 V. The amplitude was set at 0.01 V. The obtained impedance spectra were fitted to an equivalent circuit presented in Figure S1 (see Supporting Information) by using ZSimpWin software (Ametek, USA), where R_{sol} is the resistance of the solvent, R_{mem} is the resistance of the membrane, Q_{mem} is a constant phase element for the membrane and the Q_{sp} is a constant phase element corresponding to the submembrane region between the bilayer and Au(111) surface. The model used in this work is

a variation of the circuit proposed by Valincius and Mickevicius [17] and is identical to the one used by the Lipkowski group for electrodes modified with lipid membranes.[18,19]

2.4.Surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (SEIRAS)

The spectra were recorded with Nicolet iS50 FTIR spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) with MCT-A detector and custom-made single-reflection accessory. The incident angle was 60° with the spectral resolution set as 4 cm⁻¹. First, the prism was cleaned on a polishing cloth with three diamond polishing suspensions with diameters of 3.0, 1.0, and 0.25 μm. After polishing steps, the prisms were washed with water and kept for 30 min in an ultrasonic bath in ethanol. Later the prisms were washed with water and 1 ml of 2% HF was dropped on top of the hemisphere prism and left for 5 mins. In the meantime, the plating solution was prepared. Such solution contains 100 μl of an aqueous sodium tetrachloroaurate solution of NaAuCl₄ • 2H₂O (120 mg/mL), 1 ml of an aqueous 2% HF solution, and 2 ml of solution containing 0.15 M Na₂SO₃, 0.05 M Na₂S₂O₃, and 0.05 M NH₄Cl. Immediately after removing the HF from the surface of the prism, 1 ml of the plating solution was applied to the surface and left for about 40-60 s. Subsequently, prisms were gently transferred into a glass crystallizer with ultrapure water. A freshly prepared prism with a gold layer was put in the holder and 1 ml of ChLL solution was added to the prism and spectra were collected after 2 h of self-assembly (before collecting spectra the modified surface was washed with D₂O). Next, either liposomes or proteoliposomes hydrated with PBS in D₂O were added on top of the modified prism, left for the ~16h, washed by a new portion of PBS in D₂O, and IR spectra were collected. The spectra are displayed in absorbance units defined as $A = \log(I_0/I)$, where I_0 corresponds to the intensities of IR radiation observed for the reference spectra, while I corresponds to the intensity observed for the sample. Data processing was performed using Omnic 9 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA).

PM-IRRAS at the air-water interface

In order to obtain PM-IRRAS spectra at the air-water interface, Nicolet iS50 FT-IR spectrometer (Thermo Scientific, USA) with ZnSe photoelastic modulator (PEM) and an MCT-A liquid nitrogen cooled detector was employed. The monolayer was formed using Langmuir trough (medium size trough with the total area of 243 cm², KSV-Nima, Biolin Scientific, Sweden) placed in an enclosed Plexiglas cover assembly mounted on an optical table. The system was purged with dried air in order to assure constant vapor atmosphere. The spectra (512 scans for each experiment) were measured using Omnic software in the wavenumber range

between 4000 cm^{-1} and 800 cm^{-1} with the resolution of 8 cm^{-1} . The incident angle of the light beam was set to 70° , while PEM operating at a frequency of 50 kHz was set to 1500 cm^{-1} , which allowed for the constant modulation of the IR light between the p and s polarization. The reference spectrum is defined as the sum of the intensities ($I_s + I_p$), while the surface-specific information is obtained from their difference ($I_s - I_p$). The final spectrum is defined as $S = \frac{I_s - I_p}{I_s + I_p}$. For each measurement, the spectra were first collected for the pure subphase (without phospholipid monolayer, S_0) and then for the phospholipid monolayer (S_π) held at a constant surface pressure of 30 mN/m . The final PM-IRRAS spectrum was obtained as:

$$\Delta S = \frac{S_\pi}{S_0} \quad (1)$$

Each PM-IRRAS experiment was repeated at least three times and the background correction procedure was employed.

Langmuir trough experiments

KSV NIMA Langmuir trough with the total area of 243 cm^2 was employed to register the surface pressure – area per molecule (π - A) isotherms. The trough was equipped with two hydrophilic barriers and a Wilhelmy microbalance with a filter paper for the measurement of surface pressure with the accuracy of $\pm 0.1\text{ mN/m}$. PBS buffer was used as a subphase. After cleaning the subphase surface, lipid solutions were deposited at the air - water interface by a Hamilton microsyringe and left for 10 minutes for solvent evaporation. Then, the monolayer was compressed with the barrier speed of 10 mm/min ($750\text{ mm}^2/\text{min}$). Experiments were performed at room temperature and were repeated at least three times to ensure the reproducibility of the results.

3. Results and discussion

Electrochemical Analysis of DOPC/gA Membranes

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is a powerful tool for evaluating the quality and structural integrity of lipid membranes, particularly in identifying defects [17,23–26]. The phase angle versus frequency plot is highly sensitive to membrane imperfections, with the occurrence of a minimum in the phase angle indicating the presence of defects. Furthermore, the position of this minimum correlates with the density of defects, where a shift to higher frequencies suggests a higher defect density [17,23,24]. The impedance spectra for a pure

DOPC membrane and a DOPC membrane with 10% gramicidin (gA) are presented in **Figure 1**. The experiments were conducted at a potential of -100 mV, corresponding to the membrane's minimum capacitance and indicating optimal packing density.

Figure 1. EIS spectra (Bode plot) presenting the impedance versus frequency and the phase angle versus frequency for the DOPC membrane (black) and the membrane with the embedded gramicidin (red). The dots represent the data obtained from the experiment, while the solid line represents the fit to the equivalent circuit. The experiment was performed at the potential of -100 mV vs. Ag|AgCl.

For the pure DOPC membrane, the phase angle remains constant at low frequencies, oscillating around -80 degrees. This regime, dominated by capacitive behavior, reflects a well-ordered membrane structure with no significant defects. In contrast, the DOPC membrane with gramicidin exhibits noticeable disturbances in the phase angle at low frequencies, with a minimum observed near 3 Hz. This minimum indicates a disruption of the electric field caused by membrane defects, which in this case are attributed to the incorporation and orientation of gramicidin ion channels. These channels create transmembrane pores, introducing structural discontinuities. Notably, the position of the phase angle minimum aligns with findings from previous studies, even though the lower concentration of gramicidin used in this study resulted in fewer membrane defects [8]. The effect of gramicidin on membrane properties is evident in the impedance data. The pronounced changes in membrane properties were observed in the

context of its ion permeability, specifically its resistance. The observed values of membrane resistance were as follows: $\sim 141 \pm 12 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for DOPC membrane vs $23 \pm 3 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for the membrane with 10% of gA. This reduction in resistance, indicating increased conductivity, is consistent with gramicidin's ability to depolarize membranes by facilitating ion flow. The above results indicate that the obtained lipid membrane model deposited on a chitosan derivative cushion demonstrates functionality that can be expected in membrane systems with ion channels. At the same time, this proves the usefulness of the model employing a chitosan derivative as a polymer cushion for studying the permeability of ion membranes in the presence of ion channels.

In the subsequent part of the study, the electrochemical responses of the model DOPC/gA membrane were evaluated in the presence of calcium ions, which are known to block gramicidin ion channels. Broadly accepted mechanism of gA channel blocking by calcium ions assumes that they interact with the peptide at the channel's entrance and, due to their size mismatch, cause its blockage. As can be concluded from **Figure 2**, the interaction of calcium ions with DOPC membranes containing gramicidin significantly alters their electrochemical behavior.

Figure 2. EIS spectra (Bode plot) presenting the effect of calcium on the DOPC membrane with gramicidin (red) after 30 minutes (dark green), and 60 minutes (green). The dots represent the data obtained from the experiment, while the solid line represents the fit to the equivalent circuit. The experiment was performed at the potential of -100 mV vs. Ag|AgCl .

The phase angle and resistance spectra, shown in **Figure 2**, were collected at -100 mV, corresponding to the membrane's maximum packing density. After 30 minutes, the phase angle minimum shifts to lower frequencies, and its depth diminishes. Such behavior, in light of the model proposed by Valincius [17,23,24], indicates a reduction in defect density. In other words, less channels are active in terms of the ion transport through the membrane. By 60 minutes, the position of the minimum remains unchanged, but its depth is significantly reduced, indicating that the membrane is partially regaining its capacitive behavior. These observations suggest that calcium ions block gramicidin ion channels, however, the membrane properties still deviate from those of pure DOPC membranes. Nevertheless, the changes occurring within the membrane are reflected in its measured resistance, which increased from a value of $23 \pm 3 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ observed for the DOPC/gA membrane to approximately $\sim 102 \pm 10 \text{ k}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ in the presence of calcium ions. This observation confirms that the electrochemical response characteristic of membrane defects is associated with the presence of gramicidin ion channels, which become blocked in the presence of calcium ions. Although the resistance increases significantly upon calcium ion interaction, it remains a bit lower than that of the pure DOPC membrane. This may result from heterogeneity of DOPC/gA membrane. It should be noted, that the presence of calcium ions is assumed not only simply block the channels but it may also induce some heterogeneity in the membrane, affecting its fluidity and inducing some structural variability on molecular level. These factors may simultaneously play a significant role in the actual mechanism of gA channel blocking by calcium ions. This issue will be discussed further in the subsequent section of the study dedicated to spectroscopic investigations.

SEIRAS Analysis of DOPC/gA Membranes

Infrared absorption spectroscopy is a widely utilized technique for detecting and confirming the presence of lipids, peptides and proteins, primarily due to the presence of prominent absorption bands associated with vibrational modes of characteristic functional groups such as esters or amides. However, when applying a planar membrane—whether with or without proteins—onto a gold electrode modified with a chitosan-lipoic acid (ChLL) cushion, conventional IR experiments are not feasible. To address this limitation, Surface-Enhanced Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy (SEIRAS) was employed as an alternative. SEIRAS enhances the infrared signal through electromagnetic field amplification near a nanostructured metallic surface, such as gold, significantly improving sensitivity for studying biomolecules and thin films [27–33]. In SEIRAS, the enhancement of the infrared signal is governed by specific selection rules, which dictate that only molecular vibrations with dipole moments

oriented perpendicular to the metal surface are amplified. This makes SEIRAS particularly sensitive to detecting structural changes or molecular interactions occurring at or near the surface. The advantage of SEIRAS technique is that the silicon hemisphere prism is coated with a thin layer of gold, effectively simulating the surface of a gold electrode enabling electrochemical control of the system. This setup allowed the modification of the gold layer with ChLL while maintaining the same properties observed during the electrochemical experiments, ensuring consistency across both spectroscopic and electrochemical analyses. For DOPC/gA membranes, the spectral region of 1800–1600 cm^{-1} is particularly relevant for analysis, as it includes bands associated with the stretching vibrations of ester bonds in lipids and amide bonds within the peptide. The corresponding spectra for DOPC/gA membranes in the absence and presence of calcium ions are illustrated in **Figure 3**.

Figure 3. SEIRA spectra recorded for DOPC/gA membrane deposited on ChLL-premodified gold-coated silicon prism before and after exposure to calcium ions. The spectra were recorded under electrochemical control at the potential of -100 mV vs. $\text{Ag}|\text{AgCl}$.

The SEIRA spectrum of the DOPC/gA membrane recorded in the absence of calcium ions exhibits a band associated with the stretching vibrations of the ester group in lipids at approximately 1734 cm^{-1} . This value is indicative of the full hydration of the polar heads of phosphatidylcholine (PC) lipids, as supported by prior literature. The hydration of polar lipid heads plays a critical role in maintaining the structural flexibility and functional properties of lipid bilayers. However, upon the addition of calcium ions, a significant shift in the ester group

band toward higher wavenumbers, specifically to 1740 cm^{-1} , is observed within just 10 minutes. The position of this band remains unchanged even with prolonged exposure to calcium ions, indicating that calcium ions induce dehydration of the polar heads of DOPC lipids. Literature evidence supports the conclusion that calcium ions, by replacing water molecules bound to the polar heads, promote a decrease in hydration [10–12]. This dehydration effect may have implications for the blocking of gA channels, as calcium ions binding to the polar heads could stiffen the region of the polar lipid heads. This stiffening effect may also enforce an enhancement of the conformational order of the lipids. Dehydration of the polar heads could also affect membrane thickness, potentially generating local mismatch conditions or increasing stress on gramicidin molecules. Increased stress on gramicidin has been described in the literature, particularly in studies by Lipkowski group, which suggest that such stress could alter gramicidin functionality [8,9]. Additionally, stiffening of the polar head region may affect the mobility of gramicidin monomers, which is a critical factor in their activity. The formation of a functional ion channel requires two gramicidin monomers to associate. These monomers align head-to-head within the lipid bilayer, forming a dimer. This dimerization is driven by the matching of their $\beta^{6.3}$ helical structures, which results in a continuous, water-filled pore that spans the bilayer. In other words, in the presence of calcium ions (Ca^{2+}), gramicidin channels may experience additional stress due to the reduced hydration of the lipid heads, increased membrane rigidity, and potentially altered mobility of gramicidin monomers. These effects may hinder dimerization or destabilize the $\beta^{6.3}$ helix, ultimately impairing channel formation or functionality.

The above considerations gain further support when analyzing the behavior of the amide I band associated with gramicidin embedded in the DOPC membrane. In a buffer solution, this band exhibits a global maximum at approximately 1629 cm^{-1} . After the addition of calcium ions, the band shifts to approximately 1634 cm^{-1} , with no further positional changes observed with prolonged exposure. The position of the amide I band peak is influenced by the strength of intramolecular hydrogen bonds and the transition dipole coupling (TDC), which in turn depends on the distance and relative orientation of the vibrating dipoles [34]. A shift of the band maximum to higher wavenumbers indicates weaker TDC and/or reduced strength of intramolecular hydrogen bonds possibly resulting from the elongation of the peptide helix. Such structural alteration may lead to a narrowing of the channel lumen and impairing the function of gramicidin ion channels. Alternatively, such conditions may favor the formation of the inactive channel conformation, e.g. $\beta^{5.6}$ helix. A more detailed insight is provided by the in-

depth analysis of the amide I band. **Figure 4** shows the comparison of the deconvoluted amide I bands before and after the addition of calcium ions.

Figure 4. Amide I region of SEIRA spectra recorded for DOPC/gA membrane deposited on ChLL-premodified gold-coated silicon prism before (A) and after 50 minutes of exposure to calcium ions (B). The spectra were recorded under electrochemical control at the potential of -100 mV vs. Ag|AgCl .

The amide I band of gramicidin A, both in pure buffer and in the presence of calcium ions, consists of several sub-bands representing different secondary structures, as revealed by deconvolution. In pure buffer, a strong band at 1629 cm^{-1} is attributed to the helical dimer ($\beta^{6.3}$ helix), corresponding to the active ion channel form of gramicidin A. Additionally, at least three other sub-bands at 1643 , 1651 , and 1666 cm^{-1} can be distinguished, which are typically associated with the double-helix conformation ($\beta^{5.6}$), representing the inactive channel form [8,9,35]. These sub-bands are less intense and form the shoulders of the dominant band originating from the $\beta^{6.3}$ helix structure. Based on peak area analysis, the population of the active channel form is estimated to be approximately 65%, consistent with previous literature reports [8,9]. Upon the addition of calcium ions, significant changes in the amide I band are observed. Deconvolution reveals that the dominant band associated with the helical dimer shifts to 1634 cm^{-1} , which, according to earlier interpretation, may indicate elongation of the helices and weakening of the intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Such elongation could deform the ion channels, impairing their functionality by altering the helical diameter. Additionally, analogous sub-bands to those observed in the pure buffer appear at 1646 , 1654 , and 1666 cm^{-1} , which can

again be attributed to alternative secondary structures of the peptide. Interestingly, the relative intensity ratios of these sub-bands change noticeably after calcium is added. The dominant peak corresponding to the helical dimer suggests that the population of this gramicidin form slightly increases to approximately 70%. However, a notable change is observed in the relative intensities of the remaining peaks. Specifically, the intensity of the sub-band at approximately 1651–1654 cm^{-1} increases significantly, while the intensities of the sub-bands at 1643–1646 cm^{-1} and 1666 cm^{-1} decrease. According to usual interpretation, this would indicate a substantial increase in the population of inactive channel forms, i.e. some fraction of $\beta^{5,6}$ double helical conformers. Nevertheless, this study proposes that the sub-band at 1651–1654 cm^{-1} does not correspond to the double-helix conformation. Instead, it is hypothesized to mark the presence of dissociated monomeric forms of gramicidin. These monomers are neither dimerized nor folded into the double-helix structure, representing a distinct, inactive form of the peptide. This novel interpretation is supported by the results of PM IRRAS measurements for gramicidin in the phospholipid monolayers, where the peptide can occur exclusively in a monomeric form [36]. The DOPC and DOPC/gA monolayers were compressed to the surface pressure of 30 mN/m, since at this surface pressure lipid monolayers and bilayers are in corresponding states with comparable molecular organization and elastic properties [37–40]. The PM-IRRAS spectra in the 1900 cm^{-1} to ~ 1000 cm^{-1} spectral region corresponding to the polar headgroup, amide bonds and carbonyl ester were recorded (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. *PM-IRRAS spectra at the air-PBS interface of a DOPC monolayer at 30 mN/m (black), a DOPC/gA monolayer at 30 mN/m (red), and a subtraction of spectrum of DOPC from spectrum of DOPC/gA (blue) in the $\sim 1900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral region (polar headgroup and carbonyl ester).*

The spectrum for pure DOPC monolayer shows a typical signal centered at 1724 cm^{-1} corresponding to the hydrated carbonyl ester (C=O) bond. Other typical bands due to the phosphate asymmetric ($\nu_{\text{as}}\text{PO}_2^-$) and symmetric ($\nu_{\text{s}}\text{PO}_2^-$) vibrations are located at 1222 and $1114/1090\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. It implies the hydration of this moiety of DOPC molecule [41,42]. Additionally, the band located at 1190 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the asymmetric C-O-C stretch of the ester groups in the β and γ acyl chains, ($\nu_{\text{as}}\text{C-O-C}$), and points to the planar orientation of C-O-C group in γ acyl chain [43]. The position of the bands is consistent with the literature reports for DOPC supported bilayers [44]. The above-mentioned bands are also observed for a DOPC/gA monolayer with similar positions and only slightly shifted towards higher wavenumbers for carbonyl ester (C=O) bond (1727 cm^{-1}) and phosphate asymmetric ($\nu_{\text{as}}\text{PO}_2^-$) (1226 cm^{-1}) vibration. However, the main difference in the spectra between the DOPC and DOPC/gA monolayers is observed in the presence of amide bands originating from the presence of gramicidin, which are located between 1700 and 1500 cm^{-1} . Since the molar ratio of gA in the DOPC monolayer is relatively low (10%), the corresponding signal is also low. Therefore, the difference spectrum obtained as a subtraction of spectrum of DOPC from spectrum of DOPC/gA is also presented in **Figure 5**. In this spectrum a broad amide I band centered at 1658 cm^{-1} can be observed. Since gramicidin A in lipid monolayers exists exclusively in the monomeric $\beta^{6.3}$ helical form, the amide I band position should be attributed to this specific form [45]. Furthermore, the localization of this band corresponds to the sub-band observed via SEIRAS in bilayers (i.e., $1651\text{--}1654\text{ cm}^{-1}$). This observation supports the notion that the DOPC/gA lipid bilayer contains populations of helical dimers, double helices, and monomers. Simultaneously, referring back to the spectral analysis from **Figure 4**, the increased intensity of the $1651\text{--}1654\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band following the addition of calcium ions reflects an increased population of monomers. This effect is not directly related to the blocking of ion channels by calcium ions but rather to the influence of these ions on the properties of the lipid membrane itself. To better illustrate this phenomenon, **Figure 6** presents the surface pressure isotherms as a function of the molecular area for a DOPC/gA monolayer, recorded on an aqueous solution of 0.01 M PBS buffer in the absence (red curve) and presence (blue curve) of calcium ions in the subphase.

Figure 6. Surface pressure vs. molecular area isotherm recorded at air-PBS interface for DOPC/gA monolayer in the absence (red curve) and the presence (blue curve) of calcium ions in the subphase.

A clear shift in the isotherm is observed upon the addition of calcium ions, indicating a reduction in the molecular area. Specifically, at a surface pressure of 30 mN/m, the molecular area for the DOPC/gA monolayer is approximately 84 Å², which decreases to 75 Å² after the addition of calcium ions. This indicates an increase in the packing density of lipid and peptide molecules in the monolayer in the presence of calcium ions, although it does not significantly affect the compression modulus. It may be explained by the fact that the presence of gramicidin itself in the DOPC monolayer already leads to a significant decrease in C_s^{-1} (Figure S2). Therefore, the effect of calcium ions cannot be clearly seen. Additionally, the presence of calcium ions does not affect the reversibility of DOPC-gA monolayer as shown by multiple compression-expansion cycles (Figure S2). Interestingly, the observed increase in packing density of DOPC-gA monolayer in the presence of calcium is consistent with the SEIRAS observations of polar head dehydration (also subtle changes occur within the hydrophobic region as explained in Supporting Information – see Figure S5). This observation has significant implications for the interpretation of electrochemical and spectroscopic data. The increased

packing density of molecules induces stress on the peptide molecules, leading to their elongation and a weakening of hydrogen bonds, as observed in the SEIRAS spectra. This structural alteration impairs the ion transport capability of the channels by narrowing their lumen. Additionally, the tighter packing of lipid molecules may reduce the mobility of peptides within the membrane, which in turn increases the population of monomeric forms of gramicidin, also evident in SEIRA spectra. This occurs because the probability of pairing or dimerization of peptide molecules from the upper and lower leaflets decreases under conditions of reduced mobility. These findings highlight the intricate interplay between calcium ion interactions, membrane structure, and peptide functionality.

Conclusions

This study provides new insights into the mechanism by which calcium ions block gramicidin A ion channels, elucidating both the structural and functional implications of this interaction. The findings, supported by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), surface-enhanced infrared absorption spectroscopy (SEIRAS), and Langmuir trough experiments, reveal a multifaceted mechanism involving calcium ion-mediated membrane modifications and direct effects on gramicidin functionality. The study highlights that calcium ions interact with the polar headgroups of the DOPC lipid bilayer, causing dehydration and increased packing density of lipid molecules. This structural modification leads to reduced mobility of gramicidin monomers, increasing the prevalence of monomeric and inactive forms. The SEIRAS and amide I band analyses reveal significant structural alterations in gramicidin ion channels upon exposure to calcium ions. By affecting the properties of the membrane, calcium ions can induce elongation of gramicidin helices and weaken hydrogen bonds, potentially destabilizing the $\beta^{6.3}$ helix. A novel observation in this study is the increase in the population of monomeric gramicidin forms in the presence of calcium ions. Unlike the conventional view that calcium ions block gramicidin channels solely by steric hindrance at the channel entrance, this study proposes that calcium ions act by altering the membrane environment and gramicidin conformation. Specifically, the increased lipid packing and reduced hydration of lipid headgroups, combined with elongation and structural variability of gramicidin, impair channel formation and ion transport efficiency. The electrochemical analysis demonstrates that calcium ions reduce density of active gramicidin channels while simultaneously increasing membrane resistance. These observations suggest a dual mechanism where calcium ions not only block active channels but also affect the surrounding lipid bilayer, reducing channel activity.

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